

A Comparative Study Between Online and Traditional Teaching

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Abstract

New methods for education in the twenty-first century have been developed as a result of educational change. Due to contemporary societal change and technology advancement, the advent of online learning in the 1990s seems to have altered the significance of conventional education. Though gaining intellectual information is often the main motivation for learning, nowadays the usability of the knowledge is the main factor that determines the learning style. Characteristics unique to both traditional and online education help shed light on their shared and distinct features. Simply said, the nature of online learning necessitates that students take charge of their own education. Conversely, the hallmark of a conventional classroom is a division of labor between teacher and student. Flexibility, engagement, communication, learning style, and skill development are all areas where the two systems vary from one another. Online learning utilizes computers, whereas traditional education relies on a physical classroom. In the end, the equivalence hypothesis shows that conventional education has more value than online education. The direct interaction between teacher and student accounts for most of the value..

Keywords: Learning, Online Classes, Traditional and Teaching Method.

Introduction

Education may take place just about everywhere, from online courses to more conventional educational institutions. Both choices provide significant advantages to students' educational experiences and are designed for essentially the same sort of learning environment. Since the birth of remote learning, there has been disagreement on whether or not online courses can effectively replace conventional classroom education. There are now various conflicting theoretical frameworks that give persuasive arguments for and against these two perspectives. Students who have busy schedules and little time to study may now get the knowledge they need thanks to the advent of online education. Web-based education has made it possible for students to get an education from any location on the globe with just a computer and an Internet connection, while conventional classes could only reach a certain number of people at a time. There are various downsides to online education compared to the conventional way of teaching that students should be aware of. On the other hand, it would seem that an increasing number of students are choosing to complete their degrees entirely online. Online education removes these limits and enables students to study whenever and wherever they want, while traditional programs are constrained by their physical locations and require students to attend class at certain times.

Online Education Origins

This trend is altering the way that professors and students engage in the classroom since an increasing number of students are utilizing the internet to augment their official education. Online education is being more emphasized at universities, and students have greater access to it in order to cater to the requirements of their populations of foreign students. According to the findings of a survey that was conducted not too long ago (just a few years ago), "there has been a substantial spike in the number of

online courses delivered by colleges" (Lundberg et al., 2008). In addition, think tanks are involved in the dissemination of information on distant education. According to findings from a study that was carried out by the Sloan Consortium, the number of students signing up for online classes saw a 17% increase between the years 2009 and 2010. As has been documented by Keramidas (2012), online education has been around for quite some time, despite the fact that it could seem to be something brand new. Around the middle of the nineteenth century, the University of London was the first institution in the world to provide distance learning and mail courses. Due to the fact that this method of instruction required the use of the postal service, it was not until the latter half of the 19th century that it became popular in the United States. The "Society to Encourage Home Studies" was created in Boston, Massachusetts, in 1873. This organization is often regarded as the first formally structured program for providing education by correspondence. Since then, other internet alternatives to traditional educational systems have matured to the point that they may now be treated seriously. The development of new technologies has unquestionably been beneficial to the field of distance learning since it has made it simpler and more comfortable for students from all over the globe to enroll in programs without having to leave their homes. McKenzie (2019) did a phenomenological investigation of instructor-student communication in online courses. During the course of her research, she differentiated and studied a number of different kinds of interactions, in addition to particular interaction difficulties. The results of this sort of research gave analytical explanations for the adoption of progressive tactics in the management of online education programs.

Advantages of Online Education

- **Flexibility-** The flexibility that comes with being able to participate in class sessions whenever and wherever it happens to be most convenient is one of the advantages of studying remotely. It is up to the student to develop their own personalized study routine that will be most beneficial to them. Simply because you don't have a lot of time does not mean that you have to make any sacrifices.
- **Commodity** - Because of the availability of this good, it is no longer required to spend time commuting to and from work each day. A student might turn their own home into a calm and serene environment in which to study and concentrate on their work. Students now have the opportunity to pick whether or not they would want to engage in the classes that are being offered. It is our duty to establish an environment that is free from disruptions from the outside world so that students may concentrate completely on the work that they need to complete.
- **Individualized Instruction-** Lessons are often given to students either one-on-one or in very small groups the most of the time (such as small groups). This approach, which is gaining popularity all the time, enables instructors to increase the quality of their lectures while also improving their understanding of the unique capabilities of each of their pupils. Every student has the opportunity to work at his or her own speed and choose an environment in which they are at ease communicating freely and truthfully with the instructor on their academic performance.
- **A Wide selection of courses** - Students have access to a plethora of different classes when they enroll in one of the many online education sites. There is a class available for students of every age or level of education, so everyone may participate. It is now possible for students to get a degree without ever having to set foot on the actual premises of a college or institution. In addition, online education makes use of a wide variety of helpful and effective teaching strategies, which allows it to cater to the requirements of each and every kind of learner.
- **Anytime everywhere educational content** - You are free to access the course materials whenever it is most convenient for you before, during, or after class. Due to the fact that they are digital, you will be able to simply access them anytime it is necessary.

- **Cost-efficient** - In the more conventional instructional methods, achieving one's educational goals requires maintaining a consistent attendance record in the classroom. People are forced to spend both their time and their money moving from one location to another as a result of this. Because of the availability of education on the internet, it is not necessary to squander either time or money on these activities.

Disadvantages of Online Education

- **Compromise, motivation and self-discipline** - It is possible that some of the pupils may have difficulty concentrating on their academic work in the absence of a schedule. Students may be instructed in self-discipline, but there are others who come to school already having it developed to their maximum potential. When you are enrolled in an online class, you may discover that you need to make some adjustments to the tasks you have been given.
- **An equipment gap in technology** - You won't go very far if all you bring along with you is a notepad and a pencil bag. You will need a computer equipped with a camera, headphones (preferred), and connectivity to the internet in order to participate in this activity. You need to make it a priority right now to get one of them if you don't already have one.
- **Hard to use in some academic fields** - There are certain courses that cannot be taken online. Certain topics, especially those that have a significant emphasis on practical application, are better suited for face-to-face conversation. However, the best results may be achieved by using both of these approaches together.

Traditional Teaching

Learning that takes place in front of a real instructor in a room full of attentive students is referred to as "conventional education," and this kind of instruction is described by that name. Under this model of education, it is required of students to physically present themselves on campus at predetermined times to engage in lectures and other activities that take place inside the classroom. The most people who may benefit from this format are those who learn best in person or who want to get the whole collegiate experience. You may always go to a guidance counselor or a professor if you feel like you need more assistance or advise while you're in school. Students are given recognition for the work that they put into each topic while they are being taught using traditional techniques of instruction, which are practiced in the classroom in such a manner as to make this recognition possible. In order to maintain order in the classroom and prevent misbehavior on the part of the pupils, rules and regulations are consistently enforced. These norms and standards originated from long-standing traditions that educational institutions had been effectively implementing for a number of years. A number of studies have focused their attention on the question of whether or not traditional classrooms or online learning environments provide more effective learning environments for students. A couple of them highlighted the benefits of high-quality education that may be attained via the use of traditional school settings (Arias et al., 2018). It is the job of teachers to disseminate information and ensure students behave appropriately within the confines of the educational setting. When I was in school, the classroom revolved entirely around the teacher since they were the only source of information for the pupils. It is built on the assumption that the sort of communication that takes place immediately in front of the classroom between a teacher and a student is the one that is the most significant kind of communication between the two parties.

Advantages of Traditional Education

- ❖ **Sociability**- Traditional schooling may reduce loneliness. The learner may feel less alone in academic struggles and gain confidence.
- ❖ **Teamwork**- The standard model of education often encourages collaborative efforts and discussions between students. Consequently, people may get insight from one another and talk

about issues that worry them. Connecting with others in this way might help spark new ideas and fresh perspectives.

- ❖ **Provides a firm strategy-** Those who struggle to maintain their own self-discipline might benefit from a consistent and straightforward study routine. The student is obligated to show up to class and put in study time at certain times in a traditional school setting.

Disadvantages of Traditional Education

- ❖ **Discipline-** There's no flexibility to create a personal calendar in order to combine studies and personal or work life.
- ❖ **Costlier Money and Time-** Commuting demands an economic expense. And if the classroom is far, time is also a factor to take into account. You have to decide whether the trip is worth it or not.
- ❖ **Large student groups lose individualization-** it's hard for a teacher to have a customized study plan fit to the needs of each individual in the group.
- ❖ **Pricier educational material-** Traditional education is more limited when it comes to educational formats. Sometimes pictures, videos or forums aren't accessible 24/7. This feature might limit the learning and hinder a good study plan.

Conclusion

Education is critical for a person's success throughout their whole life, as was said before. It makes no difference whether you are going to lessons at a traditional school or taking them online; both are equally valid options. Because of the human inclination to put more weight on the "goal" than on the "journey," a discussion over the relative merits of conventional education and online education has emerged as a result. Even while both approaches have their own unique set of advantages and disadvantages, this does not negate the reality that there is a distinction between the two strategies. As can be seen, traditional educational institutions and online educational platforms each provide their own unique set of advantages. They, too, bring their own particular challenges to the table. That means that every student who is contemplating enrolling in a degree program should carefully weigh the benefits of traditional vs online education before making their decision. When deciding whether or not to enroll in classes, a student should think about factors such as cost, convenience, flexibility, and discipline. The decision of whether to pursue one's education offline or online is ultimately up to the individual student. The acquisition of hands-on experience in a particular field or occupation is ultimately what matters the most. Students prefer traditional forms of education because they are better able to concentrate, become involved with the subject matter, and enjoy themselves in the absence of interruptions. Internet schooling was ineffective due to the significant number of issues that existed. The success of the online tactic is highly dependent on the dependability of internet connections. It has been shown that pupils are able to study more effectively in a traditional classroom environment as opposed to using a computer. Both of these opportunities are wonderful ways to broaden one's knowledge. Because of the manner in which they advise and steer their students, collect and assess student work, and conduct class discussions, students have traditionally looked up to their teachers as leaders and role models. The world moves at a breakneck speed. Additionally, schools that are receptive to technology are required. Students who take their classes online have total independence with their schedules. If teachers have the correct information, they could be able to provide students with assistance in the form of online tutoring, which would be beneficial to the students' prospects.

Educational Implications

- ✚ This research gives e-learning scholars an overview of the field.
- ✚ E-popularity learning's in today's schools may be explained by the study.
- ✚ Blended learning is an option worth considering for future classroom training.

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